

Near-infrared diffuse optical characterization of human thyroid using ultrasound-guided hybrid time-domain and diffuse correlation spectroscopies

PABLO FERNÁNDEZ ESTEBERENA,^{1,2,*}
MARTA ZANOLETTI,^{1,3} GIUSEPPE LO PRESTI,¹ GLORIA ARANDA
VELAZQUEZ,⁴ SABINA RUIZ JANER,⁴ MAURO BUTTAFAVA,^{5,6}
MARCO RENNA,^{5,7} ALBERTO TOSI,⁵
ALBERTO DALLA MORA,³ HAMID
DEGHANI,⁸ SIXTE DE FRAGUIER,¹⁰ AN NGUYEN-DINH,¹¹
BOGDAN ROSINSKI,¹¹ UDO M. WEIGEL,¹² DIBYA J. SARANGI,¹
MATTIA SQUARCIA,^{4,13} FELICIA A. HANZU,^{4,14,15} DAVIDE
CONTINI,³ MIREIA MORA PORTA,^{4,14,15} AND TURGUT
DURDURAN^{1,16}

¹ICFO - Institut de Ciències Fotòniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, 08860 Castelldefels (Barcelona), Spain

²now at Instituto de Física Arroyo Seco (IFAS), Centro de Investigaciones en Física e Ingeniería del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires (UNCPBA-CICPBA-CONICET), B7000GHG Tandil, Argentina

³Politecnico di Milano, Dipartimento di Fisica, 20133 Milano, Italy

⁴Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi I Sunyer, Fundació Clínic per la Recerca Biomèdica, 08036 Barcelona, Spain

⁵Politecnico di Milano, Dipartimento di Elettrotecnica, Informazione e Bioingegneria, 20133 Milano, Italy

⁶now at PIONIRS s.r.l., 20124 Milano, Italy

⁷now at Athinoula A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, MGH, Harvard Medical School, Charlestown, MA 02129, USA

⁸University of Birmingham, School of Computer Science, Edgbaston, Birmingham B15 2TT, UK

⁹now at Nalecz Institute of Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering, 02-109 Warsaw, Poland

¹⁰IMV Imaging, 16000 Angoulême, France

¹¹VERMON S.A., 37000 Tours, France

¹²HemoPhotonics S.L., 08860 Castelldefels (Barcelona), Spain

¹³Neuroradiology Department, Hospital Clínic of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

¹⁴Endocrinology and Nutrition Department, Hospital Clínic of Barcelona, 08036 Barcelona, Spain

¹⁵Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red Diabetes y Enfermedades Metabólicas Asociadas (CIBERDEM), 28029 Madrid, Spain

¹⁶Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), 08010 Barcelona, Spain

*pablo.fernandez@alumni.icfo.eu

Abstract: Thyroid vascularization and hemodynamics become altered in thyroid pathologies and could thus inform diagnostics, therapy planning, and follow-up. However, the current non-invasive monitoring methods available in clinics lack the necessary sensitivity and/or are impractical for large-scale deployment. As a step towards proposing a new modality, we applied the first platform, to our knowledge, designed to do simultaneous measurements of neck anatomy and thyroid microvascular hemodynamics and metabolism in a single probe placement, integrating state-of-the-art near-infrared spectroscopy techniques and clinical ultrasound. A rich dataset was formed with sixty-five subjects (forty-eight females), including eighteen healthy volunteers and forty-seven patients with thyroid nodules, characterizing thyroid tissue and the effects of demographic and anatomical variables while preserving the standard clinical workflow. We have

found marked reductions with age and body mass index in thyroid total hemoglobin concentration (*THC*), tissue oxygen saturation (*StO₂*), and blood flow index (*BFI*), among others. Patients showed lower *THC* and *BFI* than healthy subjects, and the limited sample of malignant nodules showed a higher *StO₂* than the benign. These findings support the need for personalized clinical approaches.

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1. Introduction

The most common pathologies of the thyroid show alterations in the vascularization and hemodynamics of the gland with respect to a healthy thyroid, as has been evidenced both through histopathological studies and in clinics during Doppler ultrasound (US) screening [1–4]. This includes diffuse conditions affecting the thyroid in its entirety, such as diffuse goiter, Graves' disease (GD) and Hashimoto's thyroiditis (HT), as well as focal thyroid nodules. Immunohistochemistry assays have shown that patients with GD exhibit a higher microvascular density in the thyroid than HT patients, both of them greater than normal thyroid tissue [5,6], whereas the microvascular density in thyroid cancer cases depends on nodule cytology [6–9].

Although Doppler US imaging is widely available in the clinics for thyroid assessment in routine screening, it is only recommended for the qualitative classification of vascularization patterns [10–12]. Notably, the quantitative Doppler measurement of blood flow velocity in the thyroid arteries has been found to help differentiate GD from HT and painless thyroiditis [2,3,13–15]. However, in other cases it has failed to provide useful information, showing inconsistent results among publications, low statistical powers or negative results in the discrimination between conditions or in the correlation with thyroid hormone and anti-thyroid antibody levels, which are relevant markers of disease severity and probability of relapse [13–24]. The limitations of the technique arise from its dependence on the user, the lack of standardized protocols for quantitative blood flow measurements during screening, the need for proper measures to prevent artifacts and its insensitivity to microvessels and low blood flow levels [10,11,19,25,26].

Thus, other non-invasive methodologies have been investigated to establish reliable non-subjective approaches to aid diagnosis or follow up the evolution of disease. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [27–33], photoacoustic imaging (PAI) [34–37] and more advanced ultrasound techniques (superb microvascular imaging [SMI] and high-definition microvascular imaging [HDMI]) [38–40] have been used to measure blood flow or determine microvessel structure in patients, with promising results. They have all, for instance, confirmed the differences in perfusion between GD and HT cases [36,41–43]. Nonetheless, they have not yet established the sensitivity and specificity to make a clinically relevant advancement or are hindered by their own limitations. Moreover, MRI is more expensive and not readily available for patient use, while the other methods are emerging and in the process of refining their methodologies and dealing with artifacts.

In this context, diffuse optical near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) and imaging techniques are good candidates for providing clinicians with a rich and relevant set of quantitative hemodynamic properties of thyroid tissue [44]. They are capable of probing deep tissues (1 – 3 cm from the skin) using the diffusion of infrared light, roughly in the 650 – 1050 nm wavelength range, to simultaneously gather data on its physiology, structure, microvascular flow and metabolism. At the same time, they are relatively inexpensive, non-invasive and potentially integrable into the standard screening workflow.

Among the most advanced NIRS modalities, time-domain NIRS (TD-NIRS), also known as time-resolved spectroscopy (TRS), offers the most precise and cost-effective method for the determination of tissue optical absorption and scattering properties. It employs picosecond laser pulses and single-photon detection to measure the distribution of the times of flight (DTOF) of

photons in the tissue and retrieve from that its optical properties [45–47]. Using multiple distinct wavelengths for the illumination allows the spectroscopic measurement of the concentrations of molecules present in the tissue, such as oxy- and deoxy-hemoglobin, water and lipids, which are of medical relevance.

On the other hand, diffuse correlation spectroscopy (DCS) is another NIRS technique, which exploits the intensity fluctuations of diffuse reflected light from a coherent laser source to estimate the movement of red blood cells in the probed tissue, and thus quantify microvascular blood flow [44,48,49]. The use of both techniques simultaneously has provided information on oxygenation and perfusion of tissues such as the brain, muscle and tumors, allowing the estimation of their metabolic rate of oxygen consumption [44,50,51].

The sensitivity of TD-NIRS and DCS methods to thyroid tissue (~1 cm below the skin) was first demonstrated by Lindner *et al.* [52] in twenty-two healthy subjects (ten females, twelve males) and two nodule patients (one male, one female). They established preliminary values for thyroid optical absorption and scattering, tissue oxygen saturation, hemoglobin concentration and blood flow with multispectral TD-NIRS (690, 750 and 830 nm) and using source-detector separations (SDSs) in the 1.3 – 2.5 cm range. However, they lacked concurrent anatomical information, as the placement of the optical probe was based on prior separate images. Later, Mimura *et al.* [53] implemented TD-NIRS tomography (2D array of sources and detectors) over the thyroid of a single subject (female), and used an MRI-informed discrete model of the neck to reconstruct tissue oxygen saturation maps.

The work by our group [52] set the basis for the implementation of the LUCA device, a hybrid US-guided optical platform capable of making precise measurements of a broad set of parameters [54], and which was used in this study. The lack of spatial resolution and the unknown alterations to overlying tissues due to sequential data acquisition present in non-tomographic schemes such as this [44] was addressed in our study through the use of integrated US guidance and the collection of anatomical information for each placement of the probe. This device had also been previously characterized in terms of stability, accuracy, precision and repeatability, grading it as a state-of-the-art device and proving the quality of the acquired data [54].

In this study, we used the LUCA device to obtain data on sixty-five subjects, including eighteen healthy volunteers (eleven females, seven males) and forty-seven patients with thyroid nodules (thirty-seven females, ten males), with the aim of characterizing thyroid tissue, testing the factors affecting the measurements and evaluating the capacity of the device to be included in standard clinical thyroid screening protocols. This represents the first large dataset on thyroid properties obtained through NIRS, both for the general population and for thyroid nodule patients, enabling the quantification of the effects of demographic and anatomical variables. It can thus serve as a detailed reference for future studies on the diagnosis or follow-up of thyroid diseases. We report the results of thyroid absorption, scattering, oxygenation, hemoglobin concentration, blood flow and oxygen metabolism, as well as an in-depth analysis of their dependence on demographic variables (age, body mass index [BMI], sex), geometrical and anatomical variables (source-detector separation used, thyroid depth, lobe side) and pathological state (presence of nodules, nodule malignancy).

2. Methods

2.1. Multi-modal US-guided diffuse optical device

Multi-modal diffuse optical and ultrasound (US) screening was conducted using the LUCA device (Fig. 1), which was previously tested and characterized in [54]. The device is briefly described here and details are provided in Section 1 of the [Supplement 1](#). It combines US, TD-NIRS and DCS acquisitions using a multi-modal probe with optical fibers embedded around a standard clinical US transducer of 10.6 MHz center frequency. The optode layout, shown in Fig. 1(A), provides two SDSs for each optical technique, of 1.9 (short SDS) and 2.5 cm (long SDS).

Fig. 1. (A) Picture of the LUCA device and schematic of the LUCA probe source and detector configuration around a standard US transducer. (B) Probe located for measurement over the right-thyroid lobe of a subject, fixed with a mechanical arm.

The TD-NIRS module [55] uses eight pulsed lasers in the 635 – 1050 nm range and custom single-photon detectors and electronics to reconstruct the distribution of photon times of flight.

The DCS module [56] uses continuous-wave light from a single-mode laser at 785 nm collected by sixteen channels with single-photon detectors and FPGA correlators to measure the light intensity autocorrelation function.

2.2. Study population and measurement protocol

The subjects reported in this article were recruited in the framework of the LUCA project [57], as part of a larger study focused on the contribution of diffuse-optical hemodynamic and physiological data to the diagnosis of thyroid cancer (clinical measurements are still ongoing, data not reported in this publication). Clinical measurements were performed in Hospital Clínic Barcelona following the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, with approval from the local Ethical Committee (reference number HCB/2018.0884) and by the Agencia Española de Medicamentos y Productos Sanitarios - AEMPS (reference number 694/18/EC), and adhering to the SAGER (Sex and Gender Equity in Research) [58] guidelines for reporting sex and gender information.

Two cohorts of subjects were measured: healthy volunteers and patients with thyroid nodules scheduled for thyroid extraction surgery by the Department of Endocrinology of Hospital Clínic. Prior to measurements with the LUCA device, the subjects underwent exploratory US screening, blood tests (red blood cell, hemoglobin and thyroid hormone counts), signed informed consent and reported their clinical history and demographic information. Healthy volunteers were selected by discarding pathologies (nodules, thyroid autoimmunity and/or dysfunction). The group of patients included cases confirmed as benign and malignant on anatomopathological examination after surgery, as well as patients who did not undergo surgery. Patients with nodules also underwent a fine-needle aspiration biopsy of the nodule tissue at least 20 days before their recruitment, as part of the standard thyroid cancer diagnosis. As a first step, both cohorts (healthy volunteers and patients) were analyzed jointly, as the general population typically has a large incidence of nodules, particularly in women and older subjects [59–61]. Subsequently, the differences between groups were tested.

On the day of measurement, the subjects received blood pressure and peripheral oxygen saturation (SaO_2) readings and underwent an examination with a standard US transducer, where anatomical dimensions were noted (size and depth of each thyroid lobe and nodule). Then, optical

measurements were performed by an endocrinologist using the LUCA probe with the subject lying supine on a hospital stretcher. The neck was slightly hyper-extended in a straight position (not lateralized) with the help of a towel beneath the shoulders (Fig. 1(B)) to allow the placement of the probe. An opaque lotion (Polysonic Ultrasound Lotion, Parker, U.S.) was applied to the US transducer in lieu of standard transparent US gel to avoid direct light channeling from the source to the detector fiber tips [62]. The probe was fixed with a mechanical arm to reduce motion artifacts while preserving the comfort of the subject. The subjects wore laser-safety goggles in compliance with eye safety regulations. We note that this safety measure is not a strict requirement but we opted to include it in the procedure during early *in vivo* tests.

Measurements were conducted on the left and right thyroid lobes by centering them on the US images. US imaging allowed both to identify the optimal position over the tissue to probe and to measure the depth of the thyroid below the skin in that particular placement. All nodules with diameters >1 cm (in a lobe or the isthmus of the thyroid) received additional individual measurements to compare their properties to those of a normal thyroid. Nodules <1 cm were also included in the study if they had clear signs of malignancy. Any two nodules in the same lobe were measured individually if they were well-separated.

Demographic, clinical and anatomical variables will be reported as the group mean $[Q_1, Q_3]$, where Q_1 and Q_3 are the 1st and 3rd quartiles of the distribution for the group.

TD-NIRS/DCS acquisitions for each placement of the probe lasted approximately 100 s. Two repetitions were conducted on each location, alternating sides. The starting side (i.e. the left/right lobe) was randomized to prevent possible biases due to physiological changes induced by the position maintained during the measurements.

Measurements on the sternocleidomastoid muscles on each side of the neck were also performed as reference measurements for each patient (not reported here) in the portion where they do not overlap with the thyroid, alternated with measurements on the thyroid. This optical and hemodynamic characterization was the subject of a separate publication [63].

2.3. Optical data analysis

The methodology for optical data analysis was previously reported in [63]. In summary, TD-NIRS data were fitted for each SDS assuming a homogeneous semi-infinite medium in the diffusion equation for the light fluence rate [64,65], characterized by μ_a and μ'_s values for each wavelength measured. A Mie scattering type dependence was empirically assumed for the scattering, $\mu'_s(\lambda) = A \times (\lambda/785 \text{ nm})^{-b}$, where A is the scattering amplitude and b is the scattering power [66–69]. The total hemoglobin concentration THC and the tissue oxygen saturation StO_2 were obtained from the resulting μ_a spectrum, using wavelengths of 669, 722 and 825 nm and assuming 78% water fraction [70]. This reference value was fixed, as for the chosen wavelengths the water contribution is low and does not affect the other fitted parameters [52]. In addition, the contribution of lipids to the signal was considered negligible at these wavelengths [71]. The values of the blood flow index BFI were obtained from DCS intensity autocorrelation data using the solution to the electric field correlation diffusion equation [44]. The TD-NIRS/DCS combination allowed the estimation of the metabolic rate of oxygen consumption MRO_2 coupled with the fraction of venous blood volume γ as the product γMRO_2 , which cannot be separated as γ cannot be determined for each subject [44,72]. Assuming a compartmentalized model under steady-state balance, this can be calculated as $\gamma MRO_2 = BFI(SaO_2 - StO_2) \cdot k \cdot C_{Hb}^{blood}$ [72], where $k = 1.36 \text{ ml/g}$ is the volume of O_2 per unit mass of hemoglobin for mammals [73] and C_{Hb}^{blood} is the total hemoglobin concentration in blood. Blood tests conducted on the days previous to measurements with the LUCA device provided the values for C_{Hb}^{blood} . For SaO_2 , the mean value across subjects was used, of 98% (97–99% range), which represents normal values. In addition, the differential pathlength factor DPF was calculated from the distribution of times of flight. Additional details are provided in Section 2 of the [Supplement 1](#).

2.4. Statistical analysis

The dependencies of the parameters on other variables relevant to the subjects and/or measurements were tested using linear mixed effects (LME) models. This included the effects of demographic variables (self-reported sex, age and BMI), anatomical variables (lobe/side and thyroid depth), measurement conditions (starting side and SDS used) and pathological condition of the subject/tissue (existence of nodules, their presence in a lobe and malignancy). The complete population was used to evaluate demographic and anatomical effects, whereas the groups were used to test for the effects of the presence of nodules.

The LME models considered the index of repetition (first or second placement of the probe) nested within the subject index as random effects. A random intercept for each lobe was fitted in this manner, except when the two sides were compared. This was done because a systematic difference between the sides was not assumed.

The variable to be tested for in each hypothesis was introduced as the only fixed effect each time, and tested against the null model (without this variable) using a likelihood ratio test with the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) algorithm. When the test yielded a significant difference (p -value < 0.05), the model was refitted without REML, to obtain unbiased estimates. The normality of the LME model residuals was not required, as this does not affect the fixed effect estimates significantly [74,75].

In the cases where the model failed to converge or the variance of a random effect was estimated as null (singular fit), the random effect structure was simplified to consider only the subject index (measurements from both repetitions were considered jointly), as this meant that there was not enough information in the data to estimate the variances of the full random-effect structure.

The exponential dependence of the optical/hemodynamic parameters on the continuous variables (age, BMI and thyroid depth) was also tested by considering the logarithm of the measured parameters before fitting the LME models. The fit quality was compared to that of the linear models to determine the model that best described the data.

The measured parameters for the population will be reported with the nested mean (averaging sequentially over repeated placements of the probe, sides of the neck and subjects), standard error of the mean across subjects and coefficients of variation (CV) at the levels of probe replacement, sides and subjects. The CV was calculated for each parameter x as $CV(x) = 100 \times SD(x)/\bar{x}$, where SD is the standard deviation and \bar{x} is the mean value of the parameter for the level being described. The fitted LME parameters will be reported, for each pair of measured parameter and tested covariate, through the estimates \pm standard errors of the intercept and proportionality constant between the pair, together with the p -value of the likelihood ratio test.

The continuous independent variables were tested for collinearity using Pearson's correlation test and for differences between experimental groups using paired or unpaired Wilcoxon tests, as appropriate.

The statistical analysis was performed with R Statistical Software (v4.0.0, R Core Team 2020) with "lme4" (v1.1.23), "performance" (v0.9.1) and base packages.

3. Results

3.1. Study population and anatomical measurements

The study population included eighteen volunteers without signs of thyroid pathologies (mean [Q₁,Q₃] age of 36.6 [30.5, 43.0] years, eleven females and seven males) and forty-seven patients with nodules (mean age of 48.6 [42.5, 59.5] years, thirty-seven females and ten males). The complete cohort of subjects had a mean age of 45.3 [36.0, 54.0] years (44.6 [33.8, 54.2] years for females, 47.2 [37.0, 52.0] years for males), mean BMI of 24.8 [21.0, 28.3] kg/m² (24.1 [20.9, 28.2] kg/m² for females and 26.8 [25.1, 29.1] kg/m² for males) and a female fraction of 73.8%. Table 1 summarizes the demographics of the two groups, as well as the self-reported

pathologies and blood test results. In addition, the demographic values separated by sex for each group, together with blood pressure and SaO_2 measurements, are reported in Table S1 in the [Supplement 1](#). Blood pressure (BP) and SaO_2 were normal for the general population and the sex-divided groups (123 [112, 137] mmHg systolic BP, 75 [69, 80] mmHg diastolic BP and 97.6 [97.0, 98.0] % SaO_2 for females; 130 [122, 139] mmHg systolic BP, 78 [73, 82] mmHg diastolic BP and 97.7 [97.2, 98.0] % SaO_2 for males).

Table 1. Subject demographic information and anatomical measurements performed in standard ultrasound screening (excluding nodules on isthmus). Continuous variables reported as mean [Q₁,Q₃]. An asterisk indicates a statistically significant difference between groups.

	Healthy volunteers	Patients with nodules	
Number of subjects	18	47	
Female fraction (%)	61.1 (11 females)	78.7 (37 females)	
Age (years)	36.6 [30.5, 43.0]	48.6 [42.5, 59.5]	* $p < 10^{-3}$
BMI (kg/m²)	23.3 [20.8, 24.8]	25.4 [21.6, 28.5]	
Arterial hypertension	1	6	
Diabetes mellitus	2	5	
Ischemic heart disease	0	1	
Blood Hb (g/l)	137 [128, 149]	140 [133, 148]	
Anemia (Hb < 130 g/l)	6	9	
Hematocrit (%)	41.3 [39.0, 44.0]	42.4 [41.0, 45.0]	
TSH (mIU/ml)	1.64 [1.34, 1.75]	1.68 [0.80, 2.24]	
FT4 (ng/dl)	1.19 [1.03, 1.31]	1.16 [1.03, 1.21]	
Hypothyroidism	0	3	
Hyperthyroidism	0	2	
Thyroid depth (mm)	8.5 [6.7, 10.1]	8.1 [6.5, 9.2]	
Thyroid dimensions (mm)			
Longitudinal	32.2 [30.9, 35.3]	34.9 [32.4, 37.9]	* $p < 10^{-2}$
Transverse	16.3 [14.0, 17.9]	22.7 [16.5, 28.1]	* $p < 10^{-3}$
Antero-posterior	13.6 [11.6, 15.4]	19.2 [14.1, 22.9]	* $p < 10^{-3}$
Nodule depth (mm)	-	8.5 [6.3, 10.5]	
Nodule dimensions (mm)			
Longitudinal	-	27.7 [20, 37.2]	
Transverse	-	22.4 [15.6, 30.5]	
Antero-posterior	-	18.2 [11.8, 24.4]	

Within the patient group, twenty-four subjects had a single nodule in their thyroid, fourteen had two nodules and nine had three to five nodules. Of the total of seventy-four nodules among the patients, fifty-two were found to be benign through anatomopathological examination post-extraction (belonging to thirty-two different patients, twenty-four females and eight males), thirteen malignant (in nine females and three males), five were not operated on, as surgery was not considered necessary after US and FNAB (three females and one male), and three were not confirmed by the time of analysis (two females).

The anatomical dimensions measured through US examination are also summarized for the two groups in Table 1. The depth of a thyroid lobe was considered as the approximate mean thickness of the superficial layers (skin, adipose, fascia and muscle tissues), as shown in Fig. 2, whereas the depth of the nodules can include the thickness of a layer of normal thyroid tissue if the nodule is internal to the lobe. Nodules on the isthmus were not included in the table as its anatomy is

very different from that of the lobes (four nodules). Furthermore, optical measurements on the isthmus were also excluded from the LME models, as they were conducted in a small number of cases, only when a nodule was detected in that location (four patients). The measurements on the isthmus were considered in the comparison between benign and malignant nodules. The mean thyroid depth for the complete cohort in measurements with our device was 7.7 [6.2, 8.7] mm (7.0 [6.0, 7.9] mm for females, 9.9 [8.4, 11.4] mm for males), while the healthy volunteer group had a depth of 8.5 [6.7, 10.1] mm (6.7 [6.3, 7.1] mm for females, 9.7 [7.9, 11.2] mm for males) and the patient group had 8.1 [6.5, 9.2] mm (7.0 [6.0, 8.1] mm for females, 10.1 [8.5, 11.7] mm for males).

Fig. 2. Example US images of (A) a right thyroid lobe of a healthy volunteer and (B) a thyroid nodule on a right lobe of a patient, with nearby structures. Superficial layers of skin, fat, fascia and muscle can be observed, determining the depth of the thyroid.

3.2. Measured optical coefficients and hemodynamic parameters

The measured values of thyroid μ_a , μ'_s and DPF are shown in Fig. 3 for each wavelength used and for both SDSs, and are reported in Table S2 in the Supplement 1. The measured values for μ'_s and DPF were statistically significantly different between SDSs for all wavelengths (paired Wilcoxon test, $p < 0.048$), whereas for μ_a there were differences at 637 nm and in the 840 – 1050 nm range ($p \leq 0.03$).

The eight parameters examined in the rest of our analysis were the scattering factor A , scattering power b , absorption coefficient μ_a at two of the measured wavelengths (669 and 825 nm), total hemoglobin concentration THC , tissue oxygen saturation StO_2 , blood flow index BFI and corrected metabolic rate of oxygen extraction γMRO_2 . For eighteen locations DCS measurements were discarded (six on normal thyroid lobes and twelve on nodules), as they showed a large deviation from the theoretical models for homogeneous media, and therefore the acquired data could not be fitted correctly. This resulted in a lower number of BFI and γMRO_2 data points to be analyzed for these variables compared to the rest. Possible reasons for this are addressed in the Discussion section.

Table S3 in the Supplement 1 shows the average value among subjects and the standard error of the mean (SEM) for each SDS. The value for each subject was obtained by averaging sequentially over the duration of a single measurement, over probe placements and between the thyroid lobes. The distribution of the measured values among subjects was not different from normal for μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC and StO_2 in the short SDS (Shapiro-Wilk test, $p \geq 0.38$) and for b , μ_{a-825} and THC in the long SDS ($p \geq 0.09$).

Furthermore, the variability observed in the measured variables is reported in Table S4 in the Supplement 1, at the levels of a single acquisition (during ~ 100 s of acquisition time in a single placement of the probe), between two placements of the probe in the same location and

Fig. 3. Values measured on the thyroid for the reduced scattering coefficient μ'_s , the absorption coefficient μ_a and the differential pathlength factor DPF for the long (dark green, 2.5 cm) and short (orange, 1.9 cm) SDSs measured on thyroid. Mean and SEM across subjects are plotted for each SDS.

among subjects. TD-NIRS parameters for the long SDS had mean CVs $\leq 3.9\%$ during a single acquisition, $\leq 10.2\%$ between probe replacements and $\leq 27.7\%$ among subjects. On the other hand BFI and γMRO_2 had CVs of $\leq 4\%$ during a single acquisition, $\leq 14.5\%$ between probe replacements and $\leq 71.2\%$ among subjects. The CVs for every parameter, short SDS and the subset of healthy volunteers are also shown in Table S4.

3.3. Tests of the effects of measurement parameters, demographic, and anatomical variables

The results of all fitted LME models are summarized in Tables 2 (discrete covariates) and 3 (continuous covariate), reporting model estimates and standard errors and indicating their significance. The effects tested were those of the SDS used, the side of the neck being measured, the depth of the thyroid, the subject's age, BMI and sex, the existence of nodules in the thyroid, the presence of nodules in the lobe within the patient group and malignancy of a nodule, confirmed after extraction. A more detailed description of the results is reported in Tables S5 and S6 in the Supplement 1.

The differences between parameters measured with the two SDSs were tested without considering any a priori confounding effects, as explained in Section 2.4. All parameters except μ_{a-669} showed significant differences between the short and long SDS ($p < 0.002$). Measured values and test results are also reported in Fig. S1 in the Supplement 1. In the rest of the analysis,

Table 2. LME estimates and standard errors for models with discrete covariates: SDS used, side of the neck, subject's sex, healthy volunteers vs. patients with nodules, nodules vs. nodule-free thyroid lobes in patients and benign vs. malignant thyroid nodules. Except for the SDS test, the values analyzed correspond only to the long SDS. *: p -value < 0.05.

	SDS		*	Side		*	Sex		*
	Long (2.5 cm)	Short (1.9 cm)		Left	Right		Female	Male	
A (cm ⁻¹)	8.7 ± 0.1	10.1 ± 0.1	*	8.9 ± 0.1	8.7 ± 0.1	*	8.9 ± 0.1	8.3 ± 0.3	*
b (Adim.)	0.52 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.02	*	0.52 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.02	*	0.50 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.04	
μ_{a-669} (cm ⁻¹)	0.34 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.01		0.36 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.01	*	0.32 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	*
μ_{a-825} (cm ⁻¹)	0.343 ± 0.009	0.339 ± 0.009	*	0.360 ± 0.009	0.34 ± 0.01	*	0.34 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	
THC (μM)	164 ± 5	163 ± 5	*	173 ± 5	163 ± 5	*	159 ± 5	180 ± 10	
StO_2 (%)	74.7 ± 0.4	74.3 ± 0.4	*	74.5 ± 0.4	75.1 ± 0.4	*	75.2 ± 0.4	73.7 ± 0.9	
BFI (10 ⁻⁹ cm ² /s)	8.3 ± 0.7	6.6 ± 0.7	*	9.5 ± 0.7	8.6 ± 0.8	*	9.7 ± 0.9	7 ± 2	
γMRO_2 (10 ⁻¹⁰ cm ² /s)	3.4 ± 0.3	2.8 ± 0.3	*	4.1 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.3	*	4.0 ± 0.4	3.5 ± 0.8	
	Groups		*	Nodule presence (patients)		*	Nodule malignancy		*
	Controls	Patients		Free lobe	Nodule		Benign	Malignant	
A (cm ⁻¹)	8.4 ± 0.2	8.9 ± 0.3	*	9.2 ± 0.2	8.9 ± 0.2	*	8.7 ± 0.1	9.0 ± 0.3	
b (Adim.)	0.60 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.04	*	0.48 ± 0.02	0.53 ± 0.02	*	0.48 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.04	
μ_{a-669} (cm ⁻¹)	0.38 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.03	*	0.33 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.01	*	0.31 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.03	
μ_{a-825} (cm ⁻¹)	0.38 ± 0.02	0.33 ± 0.03	*	0.35 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.02	*	0.32 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.03	
THC (μM)	183 ± 8	160 ± 10	*	165 ± 7	173 ± 8	*	151 ± 6	170 ± 20	
StO_2 (%)	74.4 ± 0.7	75 ± 1		75.7 ± 0.4	75.9 ± 0.5		74.1 ± 0.4	76.3 ± 0.9	*
BFI (10 ⁻⁹ cm ² /s)	13 ± 1	7 ± 2	*	9 ± 1	8 ± 1	*	6.2 ± 0.7	8 ± 2	
γMRO_2 (10 ⁻¹⁰ cm ² /s)	5.4 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 0.7	*	3.6 ± 0.5	3.3 ± 0.5	*	2.7 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.7	

Table 3. LME estimates and standard errors (long SDS) for models with continuous covariates: thyroid depth, age and BMI. *: p -value < 0.05.

	Thyroid depth (mm)		*	Age (year)		*	BMI (kg/m ²)		*
	Intercept	Slope		Intercept	Slope		Intercept	Slope	
A (cm ⁻¹)	8.5 ± 0.2	0.03 ± 0.02		8.5 ± 0.4	0.004 ± 0.009		8.0 ± 0.7	0.03 ± 0.03	
b (Adim.)	0.53 ± 0.03	-0.0008 ± 0.003		0.66 ± 0.06	-0.003 ± 0.001	*	0.91 ± 0.08	-0.016 ± 0.003	*
μ_{a-669} (cm ⁻¹)	0.36 ± 0.01	-0.003 ± 0.001	*	0.40 ± 0.03	-0.0015 ± 0.0007	*	0.55 ± 0.05	-0.009 ± 0.002	*
μ_{a-825} (cm ⁻¹)	0.37 ± 0.01	-0.003 ± 0.001	*	-0.83 ± 0.09	-0.006 ± 0.002	* ^a	0.58 ± 0.04	-0.009 ± 0.002	*
THC (μM)	5.16 ± 0.04	-0.011 ± 0.003	* ^a	210 ± 20	-1.0 ± 0.3	*	280 ± 20	-4.6 ± 0.9	*
StO_2 (%)	74.9 ± 0.5	-0.02 ± 0.04		78 ± 1	-0.08 ± 0.03		79 ± 2	-0.17 ± 0.08	*
BFI (10 ⁻⁹ cm ² /s)	2.23 ± 0.09	-0.034 ± 0.006	* ^a	2.8 ± 0.2	-0.019 ± 0.005	* ^a	4.2 ± 0.3	-0.09 ± 0.01	* ^a
γMRO_2 (10 ⁻¹⁰ cm ² /s)	1.39 ± 0.09	-0.038 ± 0.008	* ^a	1.9 ± 0.2	-0.018 ± 0.005	* ^a	3.1 ± 0.3	-0.08 ± 0.01	* ^a

^aestimates correspond to the LME model for the logarithm of the optical data, as a better fit was obtained.

we evaluated the results measured with the long SDS (2.5 cm), as this is more sensitive to thyroid tissue (see the discussion in Section 4.2).

The thyroid/nodules probed were on average at a depth of 7.7 [6.2, 8.7] mm, ranging from 4 to 12.6 mm. A statistically significant linear dependence on thyroid depth was found for μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC , BFI and γMRO_2 ($p < 10^{-3}$), all with a negative slope. In addition, a negative exponential dependence fitted the THC , BFI and γMRO_2 data more closely. The models are plotted in Fig. S2 in the Supplement 1 for each variable.

There was no significant difference in thyroid depth between the left and right thyroid lobes ($p = 0.92$). However, there were statistically significant differences in all optical and hemodynamic parameters between sides ($p \leq 0.002$, Fig. S3 in Supplement 1).

The effects of the demographic variables on the data were considered next. Female subjects had a higher value of scattering amplitude A and a lower value of μ_{a-669} than male subjects ($p \leq 0.04$). A decreasing relationship with age was found for b , μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC , StO_2 , BFI and γMRO_2 ($p \leq 0.04$). An exponential relation better described the dependence of μ_{a-825} , BFI and γMRO_2 on age, so these are reported in Table 3. Figs. S4 and S5 in the Supplement 1 show

the measured values vs. sex and age, together with the corresponding LME models. A decreasing relationship with BMI was found for all parameters except for A ($p \leq 0.04$), with exponential models for BFI and γMRO_2 (Table 3). The fitted dependencies with BMI showed the strongest effect sizes and are reported below for illustration in Fig. 4. Although the full data structure was considered for the statistical analysis, only one point per subject was plotted for visualization.

Fig. 4. Measured thyroid parameters vs. subject BMI. Each point is the mean value for each subject. LME fitted models are superimposed, highlighted in red and marked with "*" if the fixed effect was statistically significant. Standard error bands are shown in dashed lines. Exponential fitted relations are shown for BFI and γMRO_2 .

The presence of nodules was analyzed comparing groups and assuming initially that the hemodynamics of the entire thyroid gland of a patient could be affected by the pathological characteristics of the nodules. Enlarged thyroids could be observed in patients with nodules as well as nodules occupying the entire transverse cross-section of the thyroid. Figure 5(A) shows the mean subjects values for each group and LME models. Patients were found to have higher A values and lower b , μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC , BFI and γMRO_2 values than healthy volunteers ($p \leq 0.02$).

Within the patient population, twenty-seven patients had a thyroid lobe free of any visible lesion on US screening (six had a malignant nodule). We tested for differences in the measured parameters between nodules and nodule-free lobes in this subgroup. Figure 5(B) shows the mean points for each lobe, LME estimates and standard errors, with gray lines connecting the points of the same patient and symbols indicating the side of the neck. Thyroid lobes free of nodules had higher values of A , BFI and γMRO_2 than nodules, as well as lower values of b , μ_{a-825} , μ_{a-669} and THC ($p \leq 0.02$).

Lastly, the nodules of patients who underwent surgery and were confirmed to be benign or malignant by anatomopathological assays were used to test for the effect of malignancy. Anatomopathological examination revealed that fifty-seven out of the seventy nodules were benign and thirteen were malignant. In addition, five nodules from four patients that were not operated on due to lack of any sign of malignancy in the US (TIRADS 4A) and FNAB results (BETHESDA II) were included. They were considered benign cases, as is the standard clinical practice. Twelve of the malignant cases were papillary thyroid carcinoma cases, while

Fig. 5. Measured thyroid parameters for (A) healthy volunteer and patient groups (one point per subject), (B) thyroid lobes of patients with and without nodules (one point per lobe) and (C) benign and malignant nodules (one point per nodule). Smoothed density plots are shown next to the points with a line marking the median. In (B) and (C) light gray lines match data points from the same subject and the shape indicates the location: \bullet for the left lobe, \blacktriangle for the right and \blacksquare for isthmus. LME estimates and standard error bars are shown overlaid, highlighted in red and marked with "*" if the fixed effect was statistically significant.

the remaining one was a medullary thyroid carcinoma case. The patient index was not used as a random effect in this case, as the large majority of subjects had only one nodule. As shown in Fig. 5(C), the StO_2 values for the malignant nodules were higher than those for the benign ($p = 0.006$), while the rest of the parameters showed no statistically significant difference.

4. Discussion

4.1. Optical and hemodynamic characterization

The thyroid measurements in our clinical campaign reflected similar precision to the values obtained in a laboratory setting [54], confirming the quality of the measurements (Table S4 in the Supplement 1). For the whole population, the variability during the ~ 100 s of measurement ($\leq 4\%$ mean CV for all variables) was lower than the variability between placements of the probe ($\leq 14.5\%$), which was in turn lower than the relative hemodynamic differences among the diffuse thyroid pathologies reported in literature. Previous studies with arterial spin labeling (ASL)-MRI found 3-fold increased thyroid perfusion in GD and a 1.7-fold in HT with respect to healthy thyroids (of about 500 ± 100 ml/min per 100 g of tissue) [41]. The variation observed between subjects ($\leq 27.7\%$ for TD-NIRS parameters and $\leq 71.2\%$ for BFi and γMRO_2) was greater than that caused by repositioning the probe at the same location, thus allowing the observation of subject differences. Moreover, the inter-subject variability among healthy volunteers was lower than that for the entire study population ($\leq 22.9\%$ for TD-NIRS and $\leq 52.0\%$ for BFi and γMRO_2). These levels of variability among healthy subjects have similarly been reported in hemodynamic characterization using other techniques (ASL-MRI [28,41], dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI [32], SMI [42,43] and PAI [36]).

While TD-NIRS analysis consistently showed good-quality fits, DCS data showed a portion of the measurements that could not be fitted with a homogeneous semi-infinite diffusion model. This occurred both in measurements on normal thyroid (six thyroid lobes in six different subjects) and nodules (twelve nodules in twelve different subjects), along a large range of thyroid depth values. This was not related either to the proximity to the trachea or carotid artery, which was impossible to avoid in some cases because of the anatomical dimensions (as can be seen in Fig. 2). These autocorrelation curves showed a decay slower than exponential, so two-layer models were investigated [76–79]. Although stable fitting could be achieved, they still could not be adequately adjusted to the data. The modeling of more complex geometries using the anatomical information obtained from US images, could improve this issue in the future to recover the blood flow data for all measurements.

A comparison with the previous TD-NIRS/DCS study by Lindner *et al.* [52] showed that the values of μ_a and μ'_s were similar for the SDS in common (2.5 cm), considering wavelength interpolation. THC values were also similar, whereas our StO_2 values were higher. This could be due to the difference in the wavelengths used for estimating the concentrations, as well as the greater wavelength range used by the LUCA device to separate the optical parameters (635 – 1050 nm). In addition, our overall mean BFi value for the long SDS ($(8.81 \pm 0.09) 10^{-9}$ cm²/s) was lower than that reported by [52], which can be explained by the existing demographic mismatch. Considering only the healthy population, which was similar in age and BMI in both studies, the BFi values were in line.

Furthermore, Mimura *et al.* [53] demonstrated TD-NIRS tomography of the thyroid with three wavelengths and MRI data for medium reconstruction. This approach allowed them to recover spatial information that cannot be found using a model of a homogeneous medium. They found higher values than those in our measurements in the areas corresponding to the thyroid (in a single subject) for μ_a (at 801 nm), THC and StO_2 . Considering the contribution of other tissues to our measurements (which will be discussed later), the values are still compatible.

On the other hand, in a quantitative comparison with the data obtained with PAI, Roll *et al.* [36] reported StO_2 values in the 50 – 75% range for healthy volunteers, lower than those obtained here (74.4 ± 0.7 %, estimate \pm standard error).

In general, the large number of subjects involved in the study as well as the high precision and repeatability proved for LUCA measurements [54] support the robustness of these results. Great potential still lies in the ability to use more than three wavelengths to retrieve the concentrations of other chromophores present in thyroid and adipose tissues, such as water, lipids, collagen, thyroglobulin and tyrosine (thyroid hormone precursors) [80]. In the wavelength range used, water concentration was considered fixed as its contribution to absorption is low and the stability of TD-NIRS fitted chromophore concentrations to a $\pm 5\%$ variation in water fraction had been tested before in this range, finding negligible effects on other parameters [52]. Water fraction could vary significantly among untreated pathological cases, as water retention has been associated with hypothyroidism [81], but this is not the case of our study population, who were treated if necessary to have a normal thyroid function. Likewise, the contribution of lipids to absorption was negligible in the range used [71], but should not be disregarded for longer wavelengths. Validation of the determination of the concentrations of other chromophores is necessary to prove their robustness (e.g., with Raman spectroscopy), particularly those that contribute to absorption in lower magnitudes, and will be part of future work.

Furthermore, the anatomical information gathered with US has not been completely exploited. The shapes and sizes of the different tissues could be taken into account in the future, including the non-diffusive regions of the trachea (void) and carotid artery (highly absorbing), as has been studied experimentally in [53] and numerically in [82]. More advanced numerical analysis methods such as the Monte Carlo or finite element methods could solve the optical problem directly on segmented US images. Multi-layered simulations have been applied before to the study of NIRS sensitivity to muscle below an adipose tissue layer [83,84], but a full-fledged analysis of geometrical models would need to be applied to this more complex problem to validate the best approach.

Future work should also take into consideration possible skin tone bias, known to cause StO_2 overestimation in continuous wave pulse-oximetry for subjects with higher skin melanin concentration because of NIRS signal degradation [85–88]. This information was not recorded in our campaign and thus limits our analysis of this possible confounding factor. Nevertheless, recent studies of TD-NIRS [89] showed through systematic measurements that time-of-flight resolution provides robustness against skin tone biases.

4.2. Effects of SDS, thyroid depth, and side

The dependence of the optical and hemodynamic parameters on the geometrical characteristics of the measurements was tested through the effects of (i) the SDS used to gather the data, (ii) the thyroid depth for each particular placement of the probe (measured simultaneously with the integrated US transducer) and (iii) the location of the probe (left and right lobes of the thyroid).

The thyroid parameters reported here are statistically significantly different from those measured in the sternocleidomastoid muscle of the same subjects, published in [63] ($p < 10^{-3}$ in LME model using the subject index as a random effect, data not shown). The thyroid is highly vascularized compared with muscles and other organs [28] and we found accordingly higher THC , StO_2 , BFI and γMRO_2 values in the thyroids than the neck muscles of the same subjects. As also observed in [52], these results confirm the capability of the technology to be sensitive to thyroid hemodynamics and to detect contrast between the thyroid and other surrounding tissues.

The comparison between the two SDSs showed statistically significant differences for all parameters except for μ_{a-669} (Table 2 and Fig. S1 in the Supplement 1), with similar levels of variability observed between both SDSs (see Table S4 in the Supplement 1). Furthermore, the values measured with the shorter SDS were closer to the neck muscle values reported in [63],

which is consistent with the fact that photons collected with the short SDS are more sensitive to the layers above the thyroid than the long SDS [90]. For this reason, we considered the data of the long SDS for the remainder of the analysis.

Examining the relationship between the measurements and the depth of the thyroid (Table 3 and Fig. S2 in the Supplement 1), the negative slopes of parameters μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC , BFI and γMRO_2 also reflected the probing of thyroid tissue through sufficiently long photon paths (previously reported for THC [52]). This depth includes the thickness of both muscle and adipose tissue layers, which are less perfused than the thyroid. The individual effect on NIRS measurements of an adipose tissue layer over muscle tissue has been extensively studied in the literature [83,84,91–95]. Adipose tissue is known to have lower absorption, higher scattering amplitude A and a lower scattering power b [95–97], as this tissue has a lower THC , higher StO_2 and is metabolically less active [92,94] than muscle tissue. In particular, in our previous publication [63], the observed significant effects of the adipose layer thickness on optical variables do not match the relations found here with thyroid depth, indicating an important contribution of muscle tissue rather than adipose tissue when measuring the thyroid region. However, separating the contribution of adipose and muscle tissues in a three-layer model or more complex geometry is beyond the scope of this work, as mentioned.

Moreover, two consecutive placements of the probe at the same location resulted in substantial differences in thyroid depth for some subjects, with a mean CV between them of 7.8 – 8% (reported as well in Table S4 in Supplement 1). This was possibly the combined effect of differences in the exact location of the probe (despite US guidance) and in the pressure exerted on the tissue. Pressure reduces the distance to thyroid tissue (modifying its natural depth) and is known to induce changes in superficial hemodynamics, especially reducing the blood flow [98–100], so we cannot discard that this effect confounded our measurements. Their contribution would have an opposite sign to the estimated effect of depth, so probe pressure could be a factor to be considered in future studies.

All variables showed statistical differences between the sides of the neck (Table 2 and Fig. S3 in Supplement 1), even though there was no significant difference in thyroid depth between the two lobes. The starting side of the neck for measurements was randomized, meaning that the cumulative physiological changes occurring while the subject was lying down did not influence this result. Thus, the differences could be due to anatomical asymmetry of the neck (relative differences $\leq 13\%$). Differences in perfusion between lobes have also been observed with MRI by Schraml *et al.* [28].

The time spent in a lying position did show an effect on BFI , tested by comparing the starting side of the neck and the second side measured among patients (data not shown), with slightly higher values on the starting side (relative difference $3\% \pm 1\%$). This could be relevant in studies with long protocol durations.

4.3. Effects of sex, age, and BMI

The demographic variables sex, age and BMI showed multiple significant effects on the optical data, as shown in Tables 2 and 3, Fig. 4 (BMI) and Figs. S4 (sex) and S5 (age) in the Supplement 1. In general, these variables are not independent and are related to thyroid depth.

BMI is closely related to the amount of adipose tissue in the body, including in the neck, and was correlated with thyroid depth among our subjects (Pearson's correlation test $p < 10^{-3}$, Table S7 in the Supplement 1). In the same manner discussed for the effects of thyroid depth, a higher BMI implies a larger relative contribution of adipose tissue to the measured signals and lower relative contributions of thyroid tissues. We found negative correlations with BMI for all selected variables except for A , which is consistent with measurements through a thicker layer of adipose tissue (less absorbing, less vascularized and less active). This also agrees with the correlations with BMI previously reported in [52] for THC , StO_2 and BFI .

Moreover, the variance among patients explained by BMI in the LME models was much larger than that explained by thyroid depth (Fig. S2 in the [Supplement 1](#)). This could be because the measured thyroid depths include the variations in applied pressure between placements of the probe on the same lobe, as well as the differences between patients in the thickness of the muscle layer.

Additionally, thyroid function is known to decline with age, even in the absence of clinical or subclinical thyroid disease in the elderly [101]. Over the age of 60 years, the production of certain hormones and thyroid activity are reduced. Twelve of our subjects fell into this category, with the nuance that they were patients with nodules. We found a lower γMRO_2 in the older population, but correlations appeared throughout the age range. Moreover, negative correlations with age were found for all the same variables as for BMI. As age was positively correlated with BMI in our population (Pearson's correlation test $p = 0.02$, Table S7 in the [Supplement 1](#)), this could be an indicator of the confounding effect of BMI and the adipose tissue layer. There is also evidence that BMI may have an effect on thyroid function [102,103].

Regarding sex, differences between males and females were found in thyroid A and μ_{a-669} . Females also had a significantly lower BMI ($p = 0.02$) and thyroid depth ($p < 10^{-3}$) than males, but this was not the source of the observed differences, as it would have opposite effects. Other causes for these differences between sexes could be the muscle layer thickness and hemoglobin content in the blood (generally higher in males [104]), both of which were significantly higher in males in our population ($p < 10^{-3}$, data not shown).

4.4. Effects of the pathological state

The groups of patients and healthy volunteers were compared as a first check of the effect of the pathological condition of thyroids with nodules. However, these two groups have a demographic mismatch (see Table 1). The age difference reflects the age dependence of thyroid nodules and their high prevalence in the general population [60,105]. The high female-to-male ratio in patients is also in accordance with the population of patients with nodules [59,61]. Despite this, there were no significant differences in BMI or thyroid depth. We found higher values of A in patients with nodules as well as lower b , μ_{a-669} , μ_{a-825} , THC , BFI and γMRO_2 ($p \leq 0.048$, Table 2 and Fig. 5(A)). These differences are in line with the demographic mismatch (difference in A due to sex mismatch and in the rest of the parameters due to BMI mismatch), so it is not possible without further investigation to estimate the effect of nodules on the thyroid as a whole. In addition, our group of patients with nodules included subjects with benign or malignant nodules in one or both lobes, which could differ in their hemodynamic properties, as well as multinodular goiter cases, showing thyroid enlargement due to the presence of multiple nodules.

The subset of patients with a nodule-free lobe served to compare the altered hemodynamics of the nodules with those of normal thyroid tissue. We found differences in all variables, except for StO_2 ($p \leq 0.02$, Table 2 and Fig. 5(B)). A group comparison showed that nodules were shallower than the opposite nodule-free lobe of the same patient ($p < 10^{-3}$), which could explain some of the differences as a thinner superficial layer of tissues was probed [96]. However, the effects on BFI and γMRO_2 are opposite to the effect of loss in sensitivity to the thyroid, and thus can be attributed with certainty to nodule characteristics. They had slightly lower values for both, a trait compatible with benign nodules which represented the majority of the nodules included (75 %).

Moreover, we compared nodule data in a preliminary attempt to characterize benign and malignant nodules. A thorough investigation of nodule classification based on diffuse optical data is the objective of a larger clinical campaign with the LUCA device, which is still ongoing. Here, we considered measurements of fifty-seven benign and thirteen malignant nodules, irrespective of their cytology, including four on the isthmus. Although benign nodules were larger than malignant nodules in all dimensions ($p < 0.01$) owing to the surgery criteria, there were no statistical differences in their depth ($p = 0.07$).

We found a statistically significantly higher StO_2 in malignant nodules ($p = 0.006$, Table 2 and Fig. 5(C)). Nonetheless, this difference is relatively small ($2.3 \pm 0.8\%$) so it still calls for other sources of information and the subject variability to be accounted for by using reference optical measurements on other tissues, different SDSs or demographic correlations such as those reported here, in the efforts to inform diagnostics.

5. Conclusion

We have reported a thorough characterization of the optical and hemodynamic properties of thyroid tissue in sixty-five subjects, reference tables and statistical tests, which is to the best of our knowledge the first to be published in a large group of patients with nodules and subjects in general. The results and analysis presented here can be used as a comprehensive reference for the absolute values of thyroid optical and hemodynamic properties, the precision in their measurement, the variability within and between subjects and their dependencies on demographic variables, anatomical characteristics and the presence of nodules.

Moreover, the data gathered have further potential to study the possibility of quantifying the concentrations of other chromophores in the tissue (collagen, lipids, thyroid hormone precursors) and making use of the full geometrical information gathered with US images to improve the sensitivity to thyroid tissue and the modeling of atypical intensity autocorrelation curves. This will be a part of further investigations.

Future studies on the diagnosis and follow-up of thyroid diseases affecting thyroid hemodynamics, such as HT or GD, or the development of future hybrid optical devices to study this organ, can make use of the present characterization to design protocols and interpret the data in light of the characteristics of the population under study. The effects of demographic variables such as age and BMI on the measured parameters were found to be strong, so measures should be taken to account for these differences. In this way, we bolster the application of diffuse optical technologies in endocrinology research and provide clinicians with relevant physiological information.

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ICFO has equity ownership in the spin-off company HemoPhotonics S.L. and UMW is the CEO. TD and UMW are inventors of relevant patents.

MB, DC, ADM and AT are co-founders of PIONIRS s.r.l., a spin-off company from Politecnico di Milano (Italy), and MB is the CEO of the company. Their involvement in the study primarily preceded the company's foundation.

All potential financial conflicts of interest and research objectivity were monitored by ICFO's Knowledge & Technology Transfer Department.

Data availability. The data and analysis scripts that support the findings of this study are openly available [106].

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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